

POTENTIAL OF PEPTIDE AND ANTIMICROBIAL IN SOME TYPES OF FROGS

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Genetics is a branch of biology that studies genes and is widely known as the science of inheritance, because in genes there are segments of DNA molecules that are associated with inheritance units. In addition to studying the inheritance of traits, genetics can also learn about the molecules that make up the structure of living things. Like knowing the content contained in frog secretions, fingerprint patterns in humans even identify plants molecularly. To test the object that we want to do and achieve the desired goal, it is possible to combine other branches of science in the work procedure. For example, to carry out resistance tests and determine the protein content in frog skin secretions, you can combine the branches of genetics and microbiology.

Talking about DNA, of course, it cannot be separated from the constituent elements contained in the DNA, one of which is a protein that plays an important role in biological processes to catalyze the biochemical reactions, movement, transport of ligands, transmit nerve impulses, and control the growth and components of the immune system in humans living things (Khan, Siddiqi and Salahuddin, 2017). To find out how the effect of protein on a reaction can be observed through experiments using several test mycobacteria that will give different results to the mycobacteria used. This can be caused by the content of the protein contained in the object to be used, and it can also be known whether the protein contains Antimicrobial Peptide (AMP) which can be a solution for various currently resistant drugs. By combining the fields of genetics and microbiology, it can be seen what the protein and antimicrobial potential of several types of frogs are.

Global problems in the health sector that are being faced today are infections caused by pathogenic bacteria and fungi. Treatment that can be done in overcoming these diseases is by giving antibiotics. However, uncontrolled use of antibiotics causes certain bacteria and fungi to become resistant. Compounds that have potential as natural antimicrobials are alkaloids, proteins, peptides, and steroids. These compounds can be found in frog skin secretions (Sciani *et al.*, 2013). One of the compounds that have potential as antimicrobials in frog skin secretions is peptide. Antimicrobial Peptide (AMP) is a molecule produced by body tissue cells (Sejati, 2015). AMP is an important component of the immune system defense to protect organisms from pathogenic microbes (Bulet, Stocklin and Menin, 2004). So that AMP can be used as an alternative that can be used as a solution to the problem of resistance globally in this century.

One of the vertebrate groups that produce AMP compounds secreted from the skin is frogs. Frog skin is rich in biologically active compounds (Govender *et al.*, 2012). One type of frog that has the potential as an antimicrobial is *Limnonectes blythii* which is a species that is widespread in Southeast Asia from Myanmar, Thailand, peninsular Malaysia, and northern Sumatra (Tjong, Iskandar, and Gusman, 2010). One of the techniques used to determine the peptide content of frog secrets is *Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate Polyacrylamide Gel* (SDS PAGE). Research on this has been carried out by several researchers using the SDS-PAGE method. Oktavina and Pratiwi (2015) reported that there were differences in protein banding pattern in the frogs *Phrynoidis aspera*, *Ingerophrynus biporcatus*, *Duttaphrynus melanostictus* and in the skin secretions of the frog *Odorrana hosii* via SDS-PAGE, that the distribution of molecular

weight from the electrophoresis results of the secretion of *Pletodon shermani* (Caudata, Plethodontidae) between 10 and 170 kDa. Furthermore Jared *et al.* (2018) stated that there were differences in protein profiles in *Siphonops annulatus* (Cecilia) on the head and on the posterior.

Several studies on the potential of antimicrobial compounds in frog culture in Indonesia have also been reported, including by Artika, Pinantoan, and Kusriani (2015) who reported that the secretions on the skin of frogs *Leptophryne cruentata* and *Rhacophorus margaritifer* were able to inhibit the growth of Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*), Gram positive bacteria (*S. aureus*) and the fungus *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*. Suhyana, Artika, and Safan (2015) reported that the skin secretions of *Limnonectes macrodon* frogs did not show antibacterial activity against drug-resistant *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (MDR)SPN1307, while the secretions on the skin of the frog *Fejervarya limnocharis* showed antibacterial activity against *S. pneumoniae* Multi Drug Resistant (MDR) SPN1307, but smaller than the positive control used. Feskaharny *et al* (2020) also reported that the skin secretions of *Rana hosii* frogs have the potential as broad-spectrum antibacterial, with the largest inhibition zone of 11.74 mm against *E. coli* obtained from the ratio of secretions: solvent 1:3 and has antifungal activity against *C. albicans*.

Many studies have proven that the presence of antimicrobials in various species of frogs can be used as a reference to find out the antimicrobial content of other species that may have antimicrobials with better peptide content so that they become a solution for existing disease resistance. The protein contained in frog skin secretions can also provide molecular genetic information.

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